

QADIRI'S TRANSLATION SKILLS

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ANNOTATION

This is it in the article Uzbek novel of the school founder Abdulla Qadiri about to be His more cool creativity again understood once _ without , Qadiri's translation skill in particular word goes _

Base words ; Translator , translation , artistic translation , art image , literary communication , genre , originality .

ANNOTATION

This article is about Abdulla Qadiri , the founder of the Uzbek novel school. Recognizing his more prolific creativity, we talk about Qadiri's translation skills .

basic words; Translator, translation, artistic translation, artistic image, literary communication, genre, originality.

Various nations , East and West in the middle literary commonality , literary in communications artistic of translation place how much high not even that It's not a secret to anyone . 20th century years the world literature of samples Uzbek to the language translation in our country artistic of translation next development big positive effect showed . In this period mature our writers their original works Create with together , artistic translation also with engaged in , the world of literature big representatives his works Uzbek to the language translation they did A. Qadiri , Cholpon , Oybek , G' . Ghulam , H. Olimjon , Mirtemir , A. Qahhor , P. Tursun and M. Ismaili such as series of writers artistic translation to work added contributions especially weighty it has been .

Own activities at the beginning of the 20s small works and big in genres from the works fragments translation by doing started our translators were Russian in the 1930s and West literature of its manifestations series big his works Uzbek to the language translation they did The world in the 30s from literature done translations 20th century Uzbek literature in progress and especially prose _ genres is also big in development role played _ Original work with engaged in of our writers translation in the activity gained experiences own the effect gave _ As a result their pen under French to their stories special short realistic stories and Uzbek literature dovrugini to the world spread big genre works to the world came _

20th century Uzbek of literature big representative , Uzbek to the novel basis put famous writer Abdulla Qadiri past in the 20s-30s of the century his own major original works Create with one in line the world and Russian from literature Uzbek to the language translation to do is also busy with it has been . Uzbek readers Russian of literature the classics APChekhov's story " Chameleon " (" Buqalamun ") , NVGogol's comedy " Marriage " , Italian from writers Boccaccio and Mozuccio's some short stories , French writers A. Dode's

" Happy Augustine's dear " Duosi " . novella " Lourdes " and "Rome" by E. Zolya , Denis " Nun " by Diderot , American writer Mark Twain's " Luxury and begging " and " Holy Inquisition " from the novels fragments A. Qadiri in the translation own mother in the language reading luckily Musharraf will be

A. Qadiri French from literature done translations translator of our scientists in his studies analysis done _ In particular , Maupassant's novel " Normandy " . translation Y. Polatov in his dissertation [1], from the novels " Lourdes " and "Rim" by E. Zolya translation done fragments R.Shirinova's see [2] in his dissertation developed _

Alphonse Abdullah Qadiri of Dode published in translation . " Happy Augustine dear duosi " (" Elixir ego prepodobiya ottsa Goshe ") novella plot based on tragedy destiny , person tragedy lies [3]. The main character in his work Goshe is a father His image in translation complete reflection carry on of the work ideological features understanding for how important have it's not a secret . " Translation is this losses art , - he said was famous translator M. Lozinsky . - What loss is it possible - is it artistic? or accuracy , this translator chooses _ Losses how much less if so , the translator's skill that's all is high " [4].

Qadiri in his original work of analogy different forms - metaphor , metonymy and another artistic image of means skillfully used very good we know Writer himself done increased another them in translations too fruitful uses _ "Abdullah Qadiri's translation style special one of the sususiyats of translation main to the rules compliance is doing . Forget it in translations only word in the selection skilled , humorous images in creation only estedod no , that's it with together the color of the language is logical tools of the scope width , meaning their extortions save to stay has been we also observe the longing " [6:14].

Abdulla Qadiri Russian proverb , proverb , idiom , proverb _ _ of compounds exactly that's it the meaning reflection which makes Uzbek in the language equivalents skillfully found uses _ We analyze he is also a translator in the translation of the novella he is doing proverb and materials Uzbek to the language mohitona turned _ Including Russian _ the head monk in the text with Goshe between in conversation monk Goshen calms down it is " Est sredstva vse uladit " saying encouragement gives [5:388]. A. Qadiri this the sentence Uzbek to the language according to qui turns : " Har one of pain one possible there is " [3:27].

A. Qadiri the world literature from samples translation did of works list preserved the rest This list the writer personally own hand with made up It was in 1937 writer to prison from being taken before UzSSR State To the publisher submitted . This is it in the list of foreign writers another works row French of writers there are also works . Theirs some " Dinga against artistic is included in the " works " collection .

Asfusky , this of works which in years translation done not specified . However they are twentieth of years second half and the thirtieth of years At the beginning of done that it is increased picture to do difficult it's not . In this period Uzbek language strong changes b increased he forgave That's it in periods book reader for the translation is there let it stand own mother in the language simple understandable works finish must was _ " 20 years " simple " , " understandable " translation done works good works calculated . That's why works for _ Russian from the language Uzbek to the language overturning translators them extremely simple and understandable to be for diligently movement those who did ... Translators translation during Russian in the language difficult texts down leaving Uzbek _ to his students understandable to be for some sentences add more than themselves were " .

Such Abdulla Qadiri also depends on the situation looking the work held _ Writer translation being done of the text some sentences , phrases they are translation for difficulty gave birth to for not but _ Uzbek to his student understandable to make , the main idea of the work , its meaning to him deliver intending reduced only _ In translations some disadvantages not only Abdullah Qadiri's translation activity , maybe 20-30 years creativity did almost all Uzbek to translators special was _ At this time new period Uzbek artistic translation his first steps put is still _ Uzbek translation to the theory hand not hit , his method and principles work not released was _ Even translation to practice about there are no manuals or literature was _

That's it despite that's it period the world Abdulla Qadiri from literature such as translators done increased translations Uzbek people in his life huge spiritual and educational importance occupation did _ These translations are from the 20th century Uzbek literature in progress and , in particular , prose genres is also big in development role played _ " Uzbek writers Russian and the world from literature translation to do during they are also new realistic write prose , dramaturgy , novella secrets learn they started As a result Uzbek translation of literature birth and formation in the process Uzbek Europe in literature type realistic prose examples , dramatic works appear be started "

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